

OLONITE QUESTIONNAIRE, SURVEY AND OBSERVATION RESPONSE EXTRACT

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INTRODUCTION

Many research have only focused on a single way of analysing the collected data when other available data are available. This study proposes a template for researchers who intend to use either the qualitative or quantitative means in extracting data for analysis. The template shows the unified Olonite Questionnaire, Survey and Observation Response Extract Template (UNOQESRET) in which the first segment of the template shows the Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE) the second segment shows the Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE) while the third segment captured the Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX). The UNOQESRE entails the OQRE, OSRE and the OOEX for research that entails both qualitative and quantitative. This paper recommends the Olonite Questionnaire, Survey and Observation Response Extract Template (UNOQESRET) for researchers who probably might need to extract information on a question-answer format, surveys and observation in a single research for possible triangulation.

Keywords: Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract, Olonite Survey Response Extract, Olonite Observation Extract, OQRE, OSRE, OOEX. OQSOTRE, UNOQESRET

Table 1: Unified Olonite Questionnaire, Survey, and Observation Response Extract Template (UNOQESRET)

Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE)		
S/n, S/a	Question	Response
x	xx ¹	xxx ¹
x	xx ²	xxx ²
x	xx ³	xxx ³
Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE)		
x	Question¹	
	Response xxxx ¹	
x	Question²	
	Response xxxx ²	
x	Question³	
	Response xxxx ³	
x	Observations	
Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX)		
x	i. ii. iii.	Observation xxxxx ¹
x	i. ii. iii.	Observation xxxxx ²
x	i. ii. iii.	Observation xxxxx ³

Source: Author's Design, 2022

Table 1 shows the Unified Olonite Questionnaire, Survey and Observation Response Extract Template (UNOQESRET) which is the combination of the Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE), Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE) and the Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX). The UNOQESRE entails the OQRE, OSRE and the OOEX for research that entails both qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative here means observation and survey which is the secondary data while the quantitative in the paper is the primary data which the question-answer format. The UNOQESRET is to be used in studies where questions-answers, surveys and observations is to be used in a single research.

Table 2: Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE)

S/n S/a	Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE)	
	Particulars	Response
x	xx ¹	xxx ²
x	xx ¹	xxx ²
x	xx ¹	xxx ²

Source: Author's Design, 2022

Table 2. shows the Olonite Questionnaire Response Extract (OQRE) as a single entity. This is used to retrieve questions-answers responses which is categorized as a quantitative form. The quantitative in this paper is the primary data. The OQRE is to be used in studies where questions-answers format is to be used in a single research.

Table 3: Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE)

S/n S/a	Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE)
x	Question¹
	Response xxxx ¹
x	Question²
	Response xxxx ²
x	Question³
	Response xxxx ³

Source: Author's Design, 2022

Table 3. shows the Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE) as a single entity. This is used to retrieve survey responses which is categorized as a quantitative form. The quantitative in this paper is the primary data. The OSRE is to be used in studies where verbal questions are to be asked and responses written down by the researcher. This is to be used in a single research where the respondents are unable to read nor write or where direct questionnaire filling is not feasible by the respondent. This can also be a phone survey response extract.

Table 4. Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX)

S/n S/a	Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX)
	<p style="text-align: center;">Observation xxxxx¹</p> <p>i. ii. iii.</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Observation xxxxx²</p> <p>i. ii. iii.</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Observation xxxxx³</p> <p>i. ii. iii.</p>

Source: Author's Design, 2022

Table 4. shows the Olonite Observation Extract (OOEX) as a single entity. This is used to extract information which is categorized as a qualitative form. The qualitative in this paper is the secondary data. The OOEX is to be used in studies where past events have taken place and the available data are extracted by the researcher. This is to be used in a single research where the data is available. Observation xxxxx¹⁻³ (i, ii, iii ...) means each year with its individual data.

Note:

S/n = Serial Number (1, 2, 3, 4 ...)

S/a = Serial Alphabet (a, b, c, d ...). This can also be in capital letters depending on the Researcher's choice.

x = Numerical or alphabetical Numbering of Questions

xx¹⁻³ = Questions asked (Each question that needs a response)

xxx¹⁻³ = Responses Given (Each response given to the questions asked)

Question ¹⁻³ = Questions asked (Each question that needs a response in the Survey Category)

xxxx¹⁻³ = Responses Given (Each response given to the questions asked in the Survey Category)

xxxxx¹⁻³ = Responses Given (Each response given to the questions asked in the Survey Category)

RECOMMENDATION

- i. The Olonite Questionnaire, Survey and Observation Response Extract Template (UNOQESRET) is recommended for researchers who probably might need to extract information on a question-answer format, surveys and observation in a single research for possible triangulation.